

Synthesis and Nucleophilic Addition to Conjugated Imines of 3, 5-Dimethyl-1-(*p*-anilino)pyrazole

P. S. FERNANDES, N. N. JOSHI, A. J. MENEZES,
V. D'SOUZA and V. V. NADKARNY

Nadkarny-Sacasa Research Laboratory,
St. Xavier's College, Bombay-1

Manuscript received 11 October 1976, revised 25 January 1977,
accepted 17 May 1977

IN continuation of our previous work on pyrazole derivatives^{1,2}, we have now extended the work to study nucleophilic addition on conjugated imines. Recently the synthesis and nucleophilic addition reactions on conjugated imines have been reported³.

The present communication deals with the synthesis of few imines from 3, 5-dimethyl-1-(*p*-anilino) pyrazole⁴ (Scheme I). The imines (I) gave good yields of cyanoimines (II) on treatment with potassium cyanide and acetic acid. The imines (I) were reduced to the dihydro product (III) by sodium borohydride in methanol.

Experimental

3, 5-Dimethyl-1-(*p*-anilino) pyrazole required was synthesised by the method reported in the thesis⁴. The IR spectrum (KBr) showed the absorption for $-\text{CH}=\text{N}-$ from 1540-1595 cm^{-1} . The cyano imines showed the absorption at 3430 cm^{-1} ($-\text{NH}-$) and 2245 cm^{-1} ($-\text{C}\equiv\text{N}$). The dihydroproducts (III) showed the absorption 3250 - 3300 cm^{-1} for $-\text{NH}-$. The nitro substituted derivative showed the absorption at 1520 cm^{-1} which is characteristic of NO_2 absorption indicating the presence of NO_2 . The NO_2 group does not undergo reduction during the reaction with borohydride.

Preparation of imines I (table 1) : 3, 5-Dimethyl-1-(*p*-anilino) pyrazole (0.01 mole) was dissolved in ethanol containing few drops of acetic acid, to which was added the appropriate aryl aldehydes (0.01 mole) in ethanol. The mixture was refluxed for 2 hrs. The product separated on cooling was filtered and crystallised from ethanol. Yield 60-80%.

Addition of HCN-imines (table-2) : The imines (I) 0.01 mole was dissolved in methanol and the solution was made acidic with acetic acid. A solution of pota-

Scheme I

TABLE 1

Sr. No.	R	M.P.	Mol. formula	Analysis %					
				C	Calc. H	N	Found C	Found H	Found N
1	2-OH	75	C ₁₈ H ₁₇ N ₅ O	74.23	5.84	14.43	74.08	5.81	14.14
2	4-OH	210	C ₁₈ H ₁₇ N ₅ O	74.23	5.84	14.43	74.14	5.76	14.21
3	4-OCH ₃	124	C ₁₉ H ₁₉ N ₅ O	74.74	6.23	13.77	74.58	6.26	13.56
4	4-N ₂ O	155	C ₁₈ H ₁₆ N ₄ O ₂	67.51	5.00	17.50	67.46	4.93	17.33

ssium cyanide (0.01 mole) in 10 ml water was added to the imine solution with continuous stirring at 0-5°. The precipitate (II) obtained was filtered and recrystallised from methanol. Other nitriles were prepared in an analogous way. Yield 70-80%.

Acknowledgement

Two of the authors (A. J. M. and V. D'S) are grateful for the financial assistance provided by the U. G. C. under the COSIP scheme.

TABLE 2

S. No.	R	M.P. °C	Mol. formula	Analysis %	
				Calc. N	Found
5	2-OH	133	C ₁₉ H ₁₉ N ₄ O	17.61	17.42
6	4-OH	220	C ₁₉ H ₁₈ N ₄ O	17.61	17.65
7	4-OCH ₃	162	C ₂₀ H ₂₀ N ₄ O	16.90	16.71
8	4-NO ₂	145	C ₁₉ H ₁₇ N ₅ O ₂	20.17	20.09

Reduction of imines with NaBH₄ (Table-3): Sodium borohydride (0.03 mole) was added to a methanolic solution of the imine (0.02 mole) over a period of ½ hour at 5-10°. After which the reaction mixture was allowed to stand overnight at room temperature. The excess of sodium borohydride was destroyed by the addition of water and the product was obtained by extraction with ether. The ether extract was washed with water until neutral, dried over anhydrous sodium sulfate and evaporated. The compound (III) thus obtained was recrystallised from methanol. Other dihydrocompounds were obtained in a similar manner. Yield 55-62%.

TABLE 3

S. No.	R	M.P.	Mol. formula	Analysis %	
				Calc. N	Found
9	2-OH	140	C ₁₈ H ₁₉ N ₅ O	14.34	14.19
10	4-OH	156	C ₁₈ H ₁₉ N ₅ O	14.34	14.14
11	4-OCH ₃	110	C ₁₉ H ₂₁ N ₅ O	13.67	13.56
12	4-NO ₂	113	C ₁₈ H ₁₈ N ₄ O ₂	17.39	17.31

References

1. P. S. FERNANDES, J. G. COUTINHO, K. B. COELHO and V. V. NADKARNY, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1976, 53, 498.
2. P. S. FERNANDES, S. BHATE, G. PHILIP and V. V. NADKARNY, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1976, 53, 830.
3. N. SINGH and P. S. SETHI, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1975, 52, 1079.
4. N. N. JOSHI, M.Sc., Thesis, Bombay University, 1976.

Chemical Constituents of *Aconitum violacium* and *Polygonum tomentosum*

K. P. TIWARI* and MOHAMMAD MASOOD

Department of Chemistry, University of Allahabad, Allahabad.

Manuscript received 21 December 1976, revised 2 May 1977, accepted 10 May 1977

ACONITUM (N. O. Ranunculaceae) is a large genera widely distributed throughout the Northern temperate regions. These are highly poisonous and most valuable medicinal plants¹. The literature survey of the genus *Aconitum* has revealed it to be a rich source of alkaloids²⁻⁶.

The air dried powdered roots (1 kg) were defatted with petroleum ether and then exhaustively extracted with ethanol. The ethanolic extract was concentrated to viscous mass, dissolved in acidulated water (1% HCl), the resulting solution basified with sodium carbonate and then extracted with chloroform. The aqueous solution left after the extraction with chloroform gave positive Molisch's test for the presence of sugars which were identified as glucose and rhamnose by co-chromatographic studies with authentic samples.

The chloroform extract on concentration gave a colourless solid mass which was purified by dissolving it in methanol and reprecipitating with water. The